

A Study on Industrial Tool Wear: Assessing the Potential for Optimised Lifespan Utilisation of Indexable Inserts Through Automated Wear Detection

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Abstract

This research focuses on the development of an autonomous wear detection system for indexable inserts used in manufacturing processes, with the goal of optimising tool life. The study addresses the challenge of premature tool replacement in an industrial setting, where tool lifespan is often underutilised. A prototype machine vision system was designed and tested, incorporating an 8.9 MP monochrome camera, macro lens, and deep learning software to measure flank wear. The system was validated against high-precision microscopy, revealing an average deviation of 27.4 µm. Analysis of 676 cutting edges of indexable inserts from an Austrian machine manufacturer confirmed that many inserts were retired with significant remaining lifespan, suggesting that tools are frequently replaced after only 50-60% of their potential use. The study highlights the viability of integrating such systems into industrial environments, with potential economic and environmental benefits. Future work will focus on improving measurement accuracy and expanding the dataset to further validate the hypothesis across different manufacturers and industries.

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1 Introduction

In manufacturing, the shaping of materials into products is typically achieved through conventional machining techniques, including turning, milling, and drilling. These techniques rely on the use of sharp cutting tools. Indexable inserts are commonly used in these processes due to their cost-effectiveness and versatility across various operations [1]. Tool wear is a phenomenon that occurs and develops during machining processes [2]. It has a considerable impact on the efficiency of machining processes. If not monitored, it can result in a deterioration of cutting performance and surface quality, leading to an increase in downtime and costs. It has been indicated that tool failures are responsible for unscheduled machine stoppages and 15-40% of the costs of produced goods [3]. To address tool wear, Tool Condition Monitoring (TCM) strategies are essential for extending the lifespan of cutting tools [2].

Although indirect methods are commonly employed, they often lack the precision required to determine crucial wear parameters, such as flank wear. Direct measurement techniques are more accurate than indirect methods but require manual inspection, which interrupts the machining process [4]. Consequently, there is growing interest in machine vision (MV) systems for wear detection. These systems use cameras and software to autonomously detect and analyse tool wear, offering the potential for seamless integration into machining equipment. This study explores the development of a prototype MV system designed to autonomously detect wear on indexable inserts, assessing its viability for real-world machining applications.

2 Problem Statement and Objective

Indexable inserts undergo wear and must eventually be replaced. While the replacement timing can be precisely aligned with the end of the lifespan in serial manufacturers producing the same products, this alignment is more challenging for machining companies who constantly produce different products or variants. Aside from research test setups, there is currently no precise optical in-situ method available for accurately monitoring tool wear. The interim removal of the inserts for measurement and potential reinsertion is not economically viable [5]. Therefore, often the only reference left is to estimate the end of the lifespan based on the traversed paths, the tool's engagement time or periodic replacement of the inserts [6]. Surveys conducted by the authors among European manufacturers (2024) reveal that tool replacement is often based solely on the operator's intuition and experience, resulting in a conservative approach to prevent breakage. This practice is prevalent across several European manufacturing companies, as confirmed by these surveys conducted on the shop floor.

Although numerous scientific papers have demonstrated that wear can be detected and quantified using optical methods and machine learning, and that it is possible to integrate image processing systems into machines, these solutions currently exist only in research environments and not in industry [7, 8, 9]. The actual question of what potential is lost because the inserts are replaced prematurely is still open. This work was written to explore this topic. The hypothesis is that the inserts are replaced at about 50-60% of their lifespan. The objective of this work is to confirm or refute this hypothesis.

3 Research Gaps

This study addresses the issue of determining the potential for optimising the lifespan utilisation of indexable inserts among European machine manufacturers. As previously mentioned, experts in both academia and industry, including manufacturing experts and machine operators who were surveyed during preliminary work, as well as several scientific papers, suggest that the lifespan of indexable inserts is often utilised up to only 50%. However, there is a notable lack of literature quantifying the actual potential that remains untapped in this area [5, 10].

Extensive literature exists on optimising tool lifespan for specific processes and material-tool pairings. Moreover, numerous studies have successfully demonstrated the integration of sensors, such as optical MV sensors, into machinery [11]. Nevertheless, there is a lack of research focused on the large-scale collection and analysis of used and discarded indexable inserts from multiple industrial enterprises to estimate the lost potential.

This research aims to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive assessment of the untapped potential in the lifespan utilisation of indexable inserts across various industries. This paper will serve as a kick-off for further investigations into this issue.

4 Methodology

This study focused on testing the hypothesis that the machining industry does not fully utilise the lifespan of their indexable inserts. To investigate this, a MV system was developed to monitor and evaluate tool wear. The goal was to analyse a large number of inserts from a leading Austrian machine manufacturer, specifically focusing on his two most commonly used types of indexable inserts

Data collection involved analysing 676 edges of inserts, with a subset validated using a high-precision microscope. The results provided initial insights into the potential underutilisation of tool life, confirming that this approach is a promising starting point for further studies. While the prototype demonstrated sufficient accuracy, future improvements in hardware and software were identified to enhance precision further. This research serves as an initial step toward more comprehensive studies on tool lifespan optimisation.

5 Experimental Setup and Data Collection

An industrial partner supplied indexable inserts that had been discarded after use in real machine conditions. These inserts were sourced from carbide scrap, and therefore, no specific information about the machining processes is available. The provided inserts include the 'CNMM120412-R4' type, used in turning operations, and the 'ODMT0605ZZN-D57' type, used in milling operations.

The 'CNMM120412-R4' inserts, produced by Seco Tools GmbH, are made from the TP2501 material, which is primarily designed for machining steel but is also suitable for stainless steel and cast iron [12]. The 'ODMT0605ZZN-D57' inserts, manufactured by Walter Austria GmbH, are composed of WSP45S with a

TiAlN+Al₂O₃+(Al) coating, making them suitable for both steel and stainless-steel applications [13]. It is important to note, that TP2501 and WSP45S are manufacturer-specific carbide grades.

The remaining tool life of these inserts is estimated. As stated in the ISO 3685 standard, the average flank wear width VB , and the maximum flank wear width VB_{max} can be measured to determine the wear condition [1]. For this reason, a stationary MV prototype has been developed where the inserts are manually inserted, an image of the flank face is taken, and VB is measured automatically. A total of 676 cutting edges are analysed and compared with the specified thresholds (as outlined in Table 2) to determine the remaining tool life. This prototype should be able to be integrated into the machining area or turret at a later stage, so the design must ensure that the harsh environment doesn't damage the MV system.

6 Wear Detection System

For the sake of simplicity, this system has been designed as a stationary prototype, whereby the inserts are manually placed within a 3D printed mould. This allows for the precision and potential of the used inserts to be tested prior to the system being integrated into a machine. The prototype development consisted of two main parts: hardware and software.

6.1 Hardware Design

The prototype included an 8.9 MP monochrome CMOS camera, a 1,5x macro lens, a ring light for uniform illumination and a linear stage for precise positioning of the inserts. As the system is not built into the machine at this stage, the indexable inserts have to be manually positioned in front of the optical system. To ensure that the inserts are positioned within the depth of field of the lens, the inserts are placed in a 3D printed mould mounted on a linear stage, which allows accurate positioning. The system has been housed in a tube-shaped protective housing to ensure durability in harsh machining environments on future machine integration. Figure 1 illustrates the developed prototype.

6.2 Software Development

A MV program was developed with the objective of automatically classifying the wear state of indexable inserts. The program determines the maximum flank wear width VB_{max} and the average flank wear width VB from an image of the flank face. The fundamental functions of the program are as follows: image acquisition, identification of any breakage to the cutting edge, localisation of the cutting edge, calculation of the area of flank wear, and finally, measurement of VB_{max} and VB . The MV program was developed using the MV software Aurora Vision Studio, including their deep learning platform, Aurora Deep Learning. The deep learning model is based on a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture. The pre-trained deep learning networks from Aurora Deep Learning were further trained with 100 labelled images of flank wear of the supplied inserts.

Figure 1: Prototype for flank face inspection

7 Results

A total of 676 flank faces of indexable inserts from an industrial partner, utilised in industrial machining, have been subjected to analysis.

The inserts were procured from the manufacturer's carbide scrap to closely replicate real-world conditions.

7.1 Validation of Prototype Accuracy

Given the considerable effort required to validate all inserts, only a small number were selected for microscopic measurement and validation. Eight inserts of the CNMM120412-R4 type and four inserts of the ODMT0605ZZN-D57 type were subjected to microscopic measurement. This resulted in 32 measured cutting edges for each insert type.

The InfiniteFocus G5 microscope from Alicona was used for validation purposes. However, the software provided is not suitable for measuring average wear, and therefore only VB_{max} was validated. A total of 64 cutting edges were validated, 32 of each insert, in order to validate that the same algorithm works equally well on both inserts. Table 1 displays the calculated deviation for both types of inserts.

Table 1: Deviation from the MV system

	Average deviation [μm]	Median deviation [μm]
ODMT0605ZZN-D57	26,6	20,9
CNMM120412-R4	28,4	18,1
All inserts	27,4	20,0

It is important to recognise the distinction between the mean and median deviation. The latter is influenced by the presence of flank wear patterns, which may not be consistently observed in all cases. Additionally, it is essential to acknowledge that the results of a microscopic measurement may vary if conducted by a different individual, particularly in terms of accurately determining the precise location of wear.

In consideration of the high flank wear thresholds identified in section 7.2, in comparison to the 27.4 μm deviation, the precision is deemed to be sufficiently accurate to estimate the potential for extended use of inserts.

7.2 Real Life Wear Assessment

The principal objective of this analysis is to evaluate the VB_{max} and VB of inserts utilised in industrial machining. In instances where the wear is uniform across the insert, the focus must be on evaluating the VB; however, in cases where the wear patterns are not uniform, the focus is on the VB_{max} . In particular, both maximum and average flank wear can determine whether the tool has reached the end of its life, with both values being compared against predefined thresholds [1].

Figure 2 illustrates the outcomes for both inserts. The results are presented in the form of bar graphs, which illustrate the number of indexable inserts for each of the seven categories. The first five categories represent equal intervals of the maximum permissible threshold for VB_{max} and VB. The values for these thresholds are presented in Table 2. The thresholds for CNMM120412-R4 turning inserts are based on the ISO 3685 standard. For ODMT0605ZZN-D57 milling inserts, the average wear threshold is based on the ISO 8688-1 standard, while the maximum wear threshold is based on the *Praxis der Zerspanungstechnik* textbook, which is more conservative than the ISO 8688-1 standard [14, 15, 16].

Table 2: Permissible flank wear thresholds

CNMM120412-R4	Threshold average wear	300 μm	[14]
	Threshold maximum wear	600 μm	[14]
ODMT0605ZZN-D57	Threshold average wear	350 μm	[15]
	Threshold maximum wear	700 μm	[16]

Figure 2: Flank wear analysis: (a): indexable insert type ‘ODMT0605ZZN-D57’; (b): indexable insert type ‘CNMM120412-R4’

8 Discussion

In this chapter, the findings of the study are critically evaluated, with particular attention to the interpretation of results, identification of limitations, and discussion of the broader implications. These considerations serve as a foundation for future research and potential practical applications

8.1 Interpretation of the Results:

The data presented in both graphs demonstrates that the majority of inserts are positioned within the first two bars, which indicates that the inserts listed there were utilised for a maximum of 40% of their tool life, suggesting that the theoretical potential of the inserts is not being fully utilised. However, stating that most of the inserts have reached only 40% of their anticipated tool life assumes a continuous linear increase in wear, which is not entirely accurate. The wear rate initially follows a degressive pattern (Phase I) due to high surface roughness peaks, and only later becomes linear (Phase II). Thus, if we assume, a linear increase from the beginning, as we do, the actual utilisation would be even less than 40%, reinforcing the point that there is considerable potential for extended use of the inserts [17].

A significant proportion of the ‘ODMT0605ZZN-D57’ inserts are classified as having a broken cutting edge. The reason for the discrepancy between the barely worn and broken cutting edges has yet to be determined. Potential causes for the high number of broken cutting edges include the use of inappropriate machining parameters or damage caused by rough handling during disposal. As the inserts are randomly selected from the carbide scrap, there is no information about the machining parameters, which limits the ability to investigate this further.

8.2 Identification of the Limitations of the Study

In order to ascertain the broader applicability of the observed potential in indexable inserts, it is recommended that inserts from a range of manufacturers be included in subsequent studies. It should also be noted that the threshold values stated in the existing literature are often quite general and may not be directly applicable to different machining conditions. Consequently, it is necessary to assess the suitability of these values for a wide range of machining parameters.

Additionally, the inserts were obtained from carbide scrap, and it is uncertain what damage might have occurred during disposal. This damage could include breakages or chipping of the inserts not caused by the normal production process but by rough handling afterwards. However, since the deep learning model identifies wear based on its distinctive appearance, it is unlikely that wear was measured incorrectly. The main concern is that some inserts may have been wrongly classified as catastrophic failures due to breakages or chipping that occurred after their actual use in machining. Future studies should aim to use inserts handled under controlled conditions to reduce these uncertainties.

8.3 Discussion of the Implications of the Results

A further validation of the results for these inserts would be facilitated by the reuse of some of the inserts that have already been tested. It is necessary to test these inserts for catastrophic failure, with careful documentation of the time to failure. This empirical approach will serve to validate the threshold values previously established in the literature. Subsequent research based on this work will involve the re-insertion of samples of the previously analysed inserts into the machine and their continued utilisation until they are no longer fit for purpose.

9 Conclusion

In the course of this study a prototype for the autonomous evaluation of wear on indexable inserts, with a particular focus on measuring flank wear in order to estimate remaining tool life was successfully developed. The principal findings indicate that the prototype exhibited an average deviation of 13% or 27.4 micrometres. Although there is scope for enhancement in the prototype's measurement precision, the current level of accuracy is considered sufficient for estimating the potential extended use of the indexable inserts. These findings have provided valuable initial insights into the lifespan of these tools.

9.1 Importance of the Results for Practice

The practical implications of these findings are of considerable significance. The prototype demonstrated that the two most commonly used indexable inserts at a machine manufacturer in Austria still had considerable potential to remain in use under real conditions. This provides substantial evidence to support the hypothesis that these inserts are frequently replaced prematurely. Although this study alone cannot yet confirm or refute the overall hypothesis, it provides a promising foundation for further investigation. The optimisation of indexable inserts has the potential to result in significant cost savings and an enhancement of production efficiency, thereby aligning with both economic and environmental sustainability goals.

9.2 Suggestions for Future Research and Further Development

It is recommended that future research focus on enhancing the precision of the prototype's measurement capabilities in order to provide a more reliable assessment of the tool wear.

Furthermore, to validate and expand upon the findings of this initial study, future work should involve the analysis of a larger number of inserts from a greater variety of manufacturers and industries. A larger dataset will help to confirm the hypothesis that in the machining industry, indexable inserts are being replaced too early.

This study represents an initial investigation that has already demonstrated the potential for extending the usage of indexable inserts. Further research, involving the re-insertion of these inserts under real-world condition is essential to deepen the understanding of tool wear and to ensure that the promising findings of this initial study can be applied across the industry.

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